

THE VELOCITY OF TRANSFORMATION OF HYDROXY-METHYLENE KETONES INTO BENZENE DERIVATIVES.

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The self condensation of hydroxymethylene acetone and hydroxymethylene acetophenone is a trimolecular reaction, whereas hydroxymethylene methylethylketone does not undergo self condensation and therefore possesses a different structure.

Condensation of formic ester with a ketone $R\text{-CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{-R}'$ in presence of sodium or sodium ethylate leads to the formyl derivative (I) which could enolise to (II) or (III).

Claisen and Stylos (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1145) have shown that hydroxymethylene acetone (II, $R = \text{Me}$, $R' = \text{H}$) and hydroxymethylene acetophenone (II, $R = \text{Ph}$, $R' = \text{H}$) undergo automatic condensation into symmetrical triacylbenzenes (*cf.* also Benary, Meyer and Chausius, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 108). Hence it was desired necessary to study the reaction mechanism of the transformation with a view to finding out whether such a condensation proceeds with a measurable velocity and whether it has any bearing on the structures of such ketones.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Hydroxymethylene Ketone.—A mixture of the ketone (1 mol.) and formic ester (1.5 mol.) was added to sodium wire (1.5 atom) in dry ether under ice-cooling. Next day the sodium compound formed was dissolved in water and freed from organic substances by extraction with ether. The aqueous solution of the sodio derivative on decomposition with dilute sulphuric acid liberated the free hydroxymethylene ketone, which was worked up as desired.

These hydroxymethylene ketones are strongly acidic (Claisen, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2191; 1888, 21, 915). They form chelated copper salt and could be titrated against alkali, while the tri-acyl benzenes are neutral bodies. Therefore the following processes were adopted to study the reaction mechanism.

Copper Titration Process.—The copper compounds of the hydroxymethylene ketones are very soluble in chloroform and sparingly so in water and therefore a direct estimation was not possible.

A definite quantity of the solution of the oxymethylene ketone under examination was pipetted in a separating funnel, to which an excess of copper acetate was added and shaken well. Thereafter the co-ordinated copper compound was extracted thrice with a definite quantity of chloroform (5 c.c.) each time until the extract was colourless. The aqueous copper acetate left unused was titrated with potassium iodide and hypo, starch being used as an indicator (*cf.* also Heiber, *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 902).

This gave us the measure of the hydroxymethylene ketone present at any particular interval. The concentrations being proportional to the volume of the hypo, it was unnecessary to find the actual concentrations.

Alkali Titration Process.—The hydroxymethylene ketones are strongly acidic. They could be titrated against an alkali and the titre at any particular moment is a direct measure of the free ketone present at that instant.

Therefore a definite quantity of the solution of the oxymethylene ketone was pipetted at definite intervals and titrated against an alkali using phenolphthalein as indicator. Due to sodium salt formation the solution acquired yellow colour at the end-point and hence the solution was diluted enough before titration.

A blank was run under identical conditions with each process in all cases.

TABLE I.

Hydroxymethylene acetone from 5 g. of acetone was dissolved in chloroform, washed, dried and made to 100 c.c. with alcohol. Catalyst=0.1 c.c. of HCl. 10 C.c. of nearly *N/20* copper acetate were added to 5 c.c. of the solution at room temperature, and the excess titrated back with 0.034*N*-hypo.

Expt.	Hypo Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_2 \times 10^{-4}$.
8.6	15.6	0 hrs.	7.0	...	...	...
10.85	15.3	81/4	4.45	2.55	11.45	7.4
11.5	15.3	25	3.8	3.2	10.8	9.7
12.0	15.2	81/2	3.2	3.8	10.2	9.5
12.7	15.2	137/2	2.5	4.5	9.5	10.1

The value of the k is fair considering the fact that the experiment is extended for a long period and that the temperature of the room varied between 22° and 27°.

TABLE II.

The ketone obtained from 5 g. acetone as in the Table I, and made to 100 c.c. in chloroform. Catalyst=0.15 c.c. of H_2SO_4 . 25 C.c. of copper acetate were added to 10 c.c. of the solution. Temperature= $49^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Strength of hypo=0.034N.

Expt.	Hypo	Blank.	Time.	a-x.	x.	2a-x.	$k_3 \times 10^{-3}$.
3'55	27'2		0 min	23'65	...	...	...
11'7	27'2		75	15'5	8'15	39'15	1'5
12'95	27'2		110	14'25	9'4	37'9	1'4
13'6	27'2		140	13'6	10'05	37'25	1'29
14'2	27'2		170	13'0	10'65	36'65	1'22
15'4	27'2		215	11'8	11'85	35'45	1'25

TABLE III.

To see the effect of concentration the ketone was obtained from 9 g. acetone and made to 100 c.c. in chloroform as in Table II. Catalyst=0.15 c.c. of H_2SO_4 . 10 C.c. solution and 25 c.c. copper acetate. Temperature= $49^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Strength of hypo=0.034N.

Expt.	Hypo	Blank.	Time.	a-x.	x.	2a-x.	$k_3 \times 10^{-3}$.
5'5	49'0		0 min	43'5	...	...	...
13'25	...		88	35'75	7'75	79'25	1'4
14'35	49'0		130	34'65	8'85	78'15	1'17
15'95	...		185	33'05	10'45	76'55	1'05
19'2	...		295	29'8	13'7	73'3	1'02
19'75	...		370	29'25	14'25	72'75	0'97
24'0	49'0		440	25'0	18'5	68'5	1'17

TABLE IV.

The ketone obtained from 6 g. acetone and taken up in dry chloroform (100 c.c.). No catalyst. 10 C.c. solution diluted with 50 c.c. water and titrated with 0.0234N-sodium hydroxide. Temperature= $45^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Expt.	NaOH	Blank.	Time.	a-x.	x.	2a-x.	$k_3 \times 10^{-3}$.
73'5	1'1		0 min.	72'4	...	...	...
15'0	...		35	13'9	58'5	86'3	7'10
12'7	...		75	11'6	60'8	84'3	3'83
11'7	1'1		110	10'6	61'8	83'0	3'96
10'2	...		150	9'1	63'3	81'5	3'96
9'1	...		200	8'0	64'4	80'4	3'86
8'3	1'1		275	7'2	65'2	79'6	3'50
7'1	1'1		355	6'0	66'4	78'6	3'90

TABLE V.

A solution of hydroxymethylene acetone obtained from 6 g. acetone in ether was dried over sodium sulphate, decolourised with animal charcoal, filtered and made up to 150 c.c. with absolute alcohol. Initially no catalyst was added but even after an hour there was no appreciable change which necessitated the addition of catalyst (0.1 c.c. H_2SO_4); and the time recorded from this moment. 10 C.c. solution were diluted with 50 c.c. water. Temperature = 30°. Sodium hydroxide = 0.0234N.

Expt.	NaOH Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_3 \times 10^{-4}$.
18.5	0.8	0 min.	17.7	...	...	...
11.4	4.0	42	7.4	10.3	25.1	1.79
9.7	...	77	5.7	12.0	22.5	1.78
8.8	4.0	107	4.8	12.9	22.5	1.88
8.0	..	173	4.0	13.7	21.7	1.72

TABLE VI.

0.371 G. pure hydroxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone (m. p. 72°) was dissolved in 50 c.c. of 90% alcohol. 5 C.c. titrated against 0.0234N-sodium hydroxide at room temperature without any catalyst.

Time in days	...	1	2	3	4
NaOH titre	...	15.8	15.8	15.8	15.8

When, however, a catalyst was added, it did not produce any effect even after four days.

TABLE VII.

A solution of hydroxymethylene acetophenone from 5 g. acetophenone in chloroform was dried and made up to 100 c.c. with dry chloroform. 25 C.c. copper acetate were added to 10 c.c. of solution. Catalyst = 0.1 c.c. HCl. Temperature = 22°-27°. Hypo = 0.034N.

Expt.	Hypo Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_3 \times 10^{-6}$
19.65	42.7	0 hr.	23.05	...	...	...
21.1	...	17	21.6	1.45	44.65	7.7
21.9	...	24	20.8	2.25	43.85	9.0
23.4	...	43	19.3	3.75	42.45	9.3
24.9	42.7	69	17.8	5.25	40.85	9.2

TABLE VIII.

A solution of hydroxymethylene acetophenone from 5 g. acetophenone in ether was dried and ether removed. The liquid so left was made to 100 c.c. with absolute alcohol. Catalyst=0.15 c.c. of HCl. 10 C.c. solution were diluted with 50 c.c. water. Temperature=45°. Sodium hydroxide=0.04*N*.

NaOH						
Expt.	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_3 \times 10^{-5}$.
18.4	...	0 min	18.4	...	...	...
15.9	1.8	67	14.1	4.3	32.5	1.55
14.6	...	136	12.8	5.6	31.2	1.15
14.0	1.8	165	12.2	6.2	30.6	1.14
13.4	...	198	11.7	6.7	30.1	1.10
13.0	1.8	230	11.2	7.2	29.6	1.10

TABLE IX.

Hydroxymethylene compound from 10 g. acetophenone was dissolved in ether, ether removed and the solution made to 100 c.c. in 90% alcohol. Catalyst=0.15 c.c. of HCl. 5 C.c. solution were diluted with 50 c.c. water. Temperature=48°. Sodium hydroxide=0.04*N*.

NaOH						
Expt.	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_3 \times 10^{-6}$.
36.5	0.5	0 min.	36.0	...	...	...
32.4	4.3	60	28.1	7.9	64.1	4.12
30.0	...	118	25.7	10.3	61.7	3.15
28.4	4.3	150	24.1	11.9	60.1	3.16
27.3	...	180	23.0	13.0	59.0	3.11
26.4	4.3	210	22.1	13.9	58.1	3.04
24.7	...	270	20.4	15.6	56.4	3.02
23.7	4.3	300	19.4	16.6	55.4	3.14
22.2	4.3	370	17.9	18.1	53.9	3.17

TABLE X.

Hydroxymethylene compound from 10 g. acetophenone was dissolved in 90% alcohol as in Table IX and divided in two equal parts of 100 c.c. each. Catalyst = 0.15 c.c. of HCl. 5 C.c. solution were diluted with 50 c.c. water. Temperature = 35°. Sodium hydroxide = 0.04N.

Expt.	NaOH					
	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_2 \times 10^{-6}$.
21.8	0.2	0 min.	21.6	...	...	...
21.4	2.0	74	19.4	2.2	41.0	3.46
20.8	2.0	138	18.8	2.8	40.4	2.50
20.1	...	173	18.1	3.5	39.7	2.62
19.7	...	204	17.7	3.9	39.3	2.57
18.7	2.0	276	16.7	4.9	38.3	2.61
18.5	2.0	308	16.5	5.1	38.1	2.51

TABLE XI.

Experiment repeated with the other half from Table X under identical conditions. Temperature = 50°.

Expt.	NaOH					
	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_2 \times 10^{-6}$.
22.8	0.2	0 min.	22.6	...	...	...
19.0	1.8	82	17.2	5.4	39.8	8.68
17.1	...	157	15.3	7.3	37.9	7.36
16.7	1.8	185	14.9	7.7	37.5	6.90
15.4	...	247	13.6	9.0	36.2	6.98
15.1	1.8	271	13.3	9.3	35.9	6.82
14.7	...	293	12.9	9.7	35.5	6.91
14.3	1.8	322	12.5	10.1	35.1	6.90

TABLE XII.

Oxymethylene acetone from 12 g. acetone was dissolved in ether, ether removed and the solution made to 240 c.c. in 90% alcohol and divided into two equal parts of 120 c.c. each. Catalyst = 1 c.c. of 0.11 N-HCl. Temperature = 30°. 5 C.c. solution were diluted with 50 c.c. water and titrated with 0.0484N-NaOH.

NaOH						
Expt.	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_2 \times 10^{-7}$.
27.6	0.1	0 min.	27.5	...	...	...
26.5	0.2	90	26.3	1.2	53.8	6.86
26.0	0.2	130	25.8	1.7	53.3	6.92
25.6	0.2	170	25.4	2.1	52.9	6.71
25.0	0.3	230	24.7	2.8	52.2	6.89
						Mean 6.84

TABLE XIII.

Expt. repeated with other half of 120 c.c. under identical conditions as in Table XII. Temperature = 20°.

NaOH						
Expt.	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_2 \times 10^{-7}$.
27.6	0.1	0 min.	27.5	...	...	...
26.9	0.2	91	26.7	0.8	54.2	4.42
26.6	0.2	130	26.4	1.1	53.9	4.33
26.2	0.2	170	26.0	1.5	53.5	4.61
25.9	0.3	227	25.6	1.9	53.1	4.48
						Mean 4.46

An approximate idea as to the temperature coefficient can be obtained from the ratio of the two velocity constants $k_{30}/k_{20} = 6.84/4.46 = 1.53$.

TABLE XIV.

Oxymethylene acetophenone from 10 g. acetophenone was dissolved in ether, ether removed and the solution made to 200 c.c. in 90% alcohol. 100 C.c. were taken for each experiment. Catalyst = 1 c.c. of 0.11N-HCl. Temperature = 30°. 5 C.c. solution were diluted with 50 c.c. water and titrated with 0.0484N-NaOH.

NaOH						
Expt.	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$2a-x$.	$k_2 \times 10^{-7}$.
24.1	0.1	0 min.	24.0	...	...	...
23.2	0.2	50	22.8	1.2	47.8	1.92
22.4	0.2	80	22.2	1.8	46.2	1.83
21.8	0.2	110	21.6	2.4	45.6	1.85
21.3	0.2	144	21.1	2.9	45.1	1.78
						Mean 1.84

TABLE XV.

Expt. repeated with other half (100 c.c.) under identical conditions.
Temperature = 20°.

Expt.	NaOH	Blank.	Time.	$a-x$.	x .	$a-x$.	$k_3 \times 10^{-7}$.
24'1	0'1		0 min.	24'0	...	...	...
23'4	0'2		46	23'2	0'8	47'2	1'32
22'9	0'2		90	22'7	1'3	46'7	1'14
22'4	0'2		130	22'2	1'8	46'2	1'12
22'0	0'2		167	21'8	2'2	45'8	1'11

Mean 1'17

The ratio of the two velocity constants gives us an approximate idea as to the temperature coefficient of the reaction. $k_{30}/k_{20} = 1'84/1'17 = 1'57$

DISCUSSION.

It will be clear from the following that the compounds of the type $X-CH:CH-OH$ and $X-CH:CX'-OH$ would condense to form tri- or hexa-substituted benzenes (IV) or (V).

Thus a molecule of the hydroxymethylene ketone would undergo automatic condensation into benzene derivative if it contains in its molecule the grouping $-\text{CH}:\text{CH}-\text{OH}$ or $-\text{CH}:\text{C}(\text{OH})-$. Conversely a ketone with no such grouping would be stable and would not undergo similar condensation.

Since hydroxymethylene acetone and hydroxymethylene acetophenone are known to undergo self condensation, they must contain in their molecule the grouping $-\text{CH}:\text{CH}-\text{OH}$ or $-\text{CH}:\text{C}(\text{OH})-$ and hence must possess the structure (II) or (III) ($\text{R}=\text{Me}$ or Ph ; $\text{R}'=\text{H}$). But the final product of condensation is a tri-substituted benzene (IV) ($\text{X}=\text{CO}\cdot\text{Me}$ or $\text{CO}\cdot\text{Ph}$) and not hexa-substituted benzene (V) (Claisen, *loc. cit.*), as such structure (II, $\text{R}'=\text{H}$) could only be assigned to these compounds.

This is in conformity with the observations of Claisen (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 309) that of the three forms (II, $\text{R}=\text{Me}$, $\text{R}'=\text{H}$) is the most stable for acetic aldehyde, as also of Claisen and Stylos (*loc. cit.*) that the compound readily undergoes self-condensation to triacetylbenzene (IV, $\text{X}=\text{CO}\cdot\text{Me}$), which readily follows from the structure (II).

Similar considerations hold good for hydroxymethylene acetophenone.

Therefore if 'A' represents the molecule of the hydroxymethylene ketone containing the group $-\text{CH}:\text{CH}'\text{OH}$, condensation to benzene derivative (IV) could take place according to one of the following schemes.

$\text{A} + \text{A} = \text{B}$ (intermediate product still containing the group $-\text{CH}:\text{CH}'\text{OH}$) + H_2O .

In scheme (i) the two reactions appear to be bimolecular consecutive reactions. It has not been possible to derive an expression connecting t , time, k , velocity constant and the concentration of A and B. For, in these cases if A is changing into B and B thereafter into (IV), A can not be measured on account of the fact that B has the same properties as A and the titre at any particular interval will always give the total quantity of A and B present together.

According to the scheme (ii) the reaction is one-sided trimolecular in which the molecules of the same substance are involved. Therefore, if a is the initial concentration of A and after a time t , x of it has changed into (IV), then

Our results show that hydroxymethylene acetone and hydroxymethylene acetophenone undergo self condensation according to the scheme (ii) and the process is a simple trimolecular reaction.

The concentration of the ketone does not affect the velocity constant to any appreciable extent (Tables II and III) but the increase in the temperature increases the velocity constant appreciably (Tables X to XV). This is in agreement with the fact that a very good yield of tribenzoylbenzene (IV, X=COPh) is obtained by heating a solution of hydroxymethylene acetophenone in glacial acetic acid (Claisen, *loc.cit.*). The nature of the solvent has an effect upon the value of the velocity constant, which falls in the following order : chloroform > absolute alcohol > 90% alcohol (Tables IV, V, VIII and IX).

The hydroxymethylene methylethyl ketone was found not to undergo self condensation. It could be distilled and obtained as a white solid. When dissolved in a solvent and titrated it showed no change whatsoever in the titre value (Table VI). Had the substance undergone self condensation, the enol concentration would have decreased and so also the corresponding titre value. Therefore, the substance can not possess the grouping —CH:CHOH or —CH:C(OH)— and hence must have the structure (II) or (III) (R = Me = R'), reaction taking place at the methylene group marked with an asterisk —CH₃—CO— $\overset{*}{\text{C}}\text{H}_2$ —CH₃. (*cf.* also Diels and Ilberg *Ber.*, 1926, 49, 158). Joshi, Kaushal and Deshapande (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 234) from the condensation of the compound with cyanoacetamide have shown that it possesses the structure (II) and not (III).

It is proposed to confirm the observations further by conductivity measurements.

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Received November 10, 1941.